

U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service

ECOS

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No common name (*Acropora retusa*)

[Range Information](#) | [Candidate Info](#) | [Federal Register](#) | [Recovery](#) | [Critical Habitat](#) | [SSA](#) | [Conservation Plans](#) | [Petitions](#) | [Biological Opinions](#) | [Life History](#)

Search for images on digitalmedia.fws.gov

Taxonomy: [View taxonomy in ITIS](#)

Listing Status: Threatened

Where Listed: WHEREVER FOUND

The National Marine Fisheries Service is the lead Federal agency responsible for managing this species. The information on this page isn't necessarily complete or up to date. For additional information on this species, including NMFS regulatory actions such as critical habitat designation or recovery planning, please visit the National Marine Fisheries website (<https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/species-directory/threatened-endangered>).

General Information

The species historical range included American Samoa, Guam, Northern Mariana Islands. See below for information about where the species is known or believed to occur.

Current Listing Status Summary

Show entries

Status	Date Listed	Lead Region
Threatened	11-12-2014	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Admini...

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» Range Information

Current Range

Zoom in! Some species' locations may be small and hard to see from a wide perspective. To narrow-in on locations, check the state and county lists (below) and then use the zoom tool.

Want the FWS's current range for all species? Click [here](#) to download a zip file containing all individual shapefiles and metadata for all species.

* For consultation needs do not use only this current range map, please use [IPaC](#).

Current range maps are only shown within the jurisdictional boundaries of the United States of America. The species may also occur outside this region.

There is currently no Current Range data for this species.

• Wherever found

Listing status: Threatened

- **States/US Territories** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur:
- **US Counties** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: [View All](#)
- **USFWS Refuges** in which this population is known to occur: Howland Island National Wildlife Refuge, Kingman Reef National Wildlife Refuge

» Candidate Information

No Candidate information available for this species.

No Candidate Assessments available for this species.

No Candidate Notice of Review Documents currently available for this species.

No Uplisting Documents currently available for this species.

» Federal Register Documents

Federal Register Documents

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title
11/12/2014	70 FR 67256-67259	Adding 20 Coral Species to the List of Endangered

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» Species Status Assessments (SSAs)

Species Status Assessments (SSAs)

No Species Status Assessments (SSA's) are currently available for this species.

Special Rule Publications

No Special Rule Publications currently available for this species.

» Recovery

- [Species with Recovery Documents Data Explorer](#)

No Current Recovery Plans available for this species.

The National Marine Fisheries Service is the lead Federal agency responsible for managing this species. The information on this page isn't necessarily complete or up to date. For additional information on this species, including NMFS regulatory actions focusing on recovery planning, please visit the National Marine Fisheries website (<https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/tags/recovery-plan>) and (<https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/species-directory/threatened-endangered>).

No Other Recovery Documents currently available for this species.

No Five Year Reviews currently available for this species.

No Delisting Documents currently available for this species.

» Critical Habitat

No Critical Habitat Documents currently available for this species.

» Conservation Plans

No Conservation Plans currently available for this species.

» Petitions

No Petitions currently available for this species.

» Biological Opinions

To see all FWS Issued Biological Opinions please visit the [BO Report](#).

» Life History

No Life History information has been entered into this system for this species.

» Other Resources

[NatureServe Explorer Species Reports](#)-- NatureServe Explorer is a source for authoritative conservation information on more than 50,000 plants, animals and ecological communities of the U.S and Canada. NatureServe Explorer provides in-depth information on rare and endangered species, but includes common plants and animals too. NatureServe Explorer is a product of NatureServe in collaboration with the Natural Heritage Network.

[ITIS Reports](#)-- ITIS (the Integrated Taxonomic Information System) is a source for authoritative taxonomic information on plants, animals, fungi, and microbes of North America and the world.

[FWS Digital Media Library](#) -- The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's National Digital Library is a searchable collection of selected images, historical artifacts, audio clips, publications, and video." +